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IMPLEMENTING MACROPRUDENTIAL INSTRUMENTS IN CREDIT POLICY – CONDITIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

The credit policy, as a written document, is a basic document in which banks define the credit products, the characteristics, the conditions for placement, the price, and the risk appetite is reflected in it. Each bank defines and implements its own credit policy according to its strategy (growth in market share and/or growth in profitability). NBNM, in accordance with the macroprudential policy, defines macroeconomic measures for the quality of credit demand. Banks were obliged to implement macroprudential measures. The research is focused on the effects of the implementation of macroprudential measures in the banking industry, as well as the new operating conditions followed by challenges. The implications are across all segments, from the purpose of the credit product, the conditions of the credit applicants for obtaining loans, defining the ratio of indebtedness in relation to income, and acceptability of income of the credit applicants.

KEY WORDS: credit policy, macroprudential measures, banks

INTRODUCTION

The banks, as financial mediators, have significant role, especially in the countries with poorly developed financial structure, in regard to the relevant supply of money and credits for the reproduction flows, which enable bridging of individual and sectorial imbalances. At the same time, they offer broad spectrum of services to natural persons and legal entities, public and state institutions, but they are also the first line of defense for preventing money laundering and financing of terrorism. With that, the banks present a substantial element that generates and reflects financial stability of one economy, society, state. On the other hand, the banks are shareholding companies, established by shareholders, who have remitted free cash resources as a capital and expect market return of the invested funds. With that, the banks are shareholding companies that are listed on the stock exchange and analogously they follow the market events and expectations, like the other shareholding companies listed on the stock exchange. The symbiosis of micro expectations and macroeconomic meaning defines the complexity of the banking management in the direction for meeting the shareholders' expectations.

In order all a.m. to be operational, the banks prepare a written document that allows unified application by all employees. That is a credit policy, as a basic written document by which the banks define the credit products, their characteristics, terms to be met by the credit applicants in order to be users of a specific product, and the price is also determined – the interest rate of the specific products. The credit policy reflects “the risk appetites” of the bank, and at the same time the bank’s strategy can be seen, if it is directed to the market penetration (and with which products) and the market share increase, or the focus is on the profitability, or both segments are realized in parallel. The credit policy also defines the level of decision making with appropriate credit bodies. From centralized decision making, through to decentralized, but sometimes combined approach is used, which can depend on products segments and/or on the placed amounts.

MACROPRUDENTIAL INSTRUMENTS IN CREDIT POLICY

Besides the individual approach in creating the credit policy, the banks must implement macro prudent measures as a minimum for fulfilling the requirements to be met by the credit applicants, or as a maximal credit exposure the bank can have to the applicants- the credit users. With that, the

macro prudent instruments present regulatory base developed by the banks according to their strategy and set goals.

The macro prudent policy is a sum of activities which basic aim is achieving and maintaining financial stability, both in the entire financial system and in the connections with the real sector, and here, the basic aim is determined by the law. The financial stability is realized by the macro prudent policy in that way that macro prudent measures strengthen the financial institutions resistance and the systemic risk is amortized.

The banking industry as a carrier in the financial system is in the focus of the macro prudent policy of the National bank. It should be noted that there is a distinction and supplementation of the National bank competencies and activities according to The Law for the National Bank, The Law for Banks, where the focus is on the maintaining a safe and stabile banking system in order to protect the deponents and other creditors that have invested funds in the banks, and the role, competencies and activities of the National bank according to The Law for Financial Stability where there is a wider scope, and besides the deposit financial institutions, the other financial non-deposit institutions are monitored as well.

The macro prudent measures determine the macroeconomic instruments which will be directed towards prevention and amortization of systemic risks manifestation, in separate segments and in the financial system as a whole. According to this, the macro prudent measures of the National bank refer at least to the following macro prudent instruments²⁶:

- The capital conservation buffers;
- The exposure limits;
- The risks managing;
- The indebtedness;
- The systemically important banks;
- The risk of exposures concentration;
- Other instruments for increasing the resistance to financial shocks and for preventing the disturbances in the banking system.

²⁶ <https://www.nbrm.mk/makroprudentni-instrumenti-na-narodnata-banka.nspix>

The measures and instruments of the National bank defined as per The Law for Banks can be also used for realizing the macro prudent policy goals according to The Law for Financial Stability.

For that reason, The Decision on macro prudent instruments for quality of the credit demand from natural persons has been made. The implementation of the Decision on macro prudent instruments for quality of the credit demand from natural persons has its own qualitative and quantitative moments. Taxatively, we shall mention some more important directions, while special analysis with calculations will be made in the part for determining the financial capacity of the natural persons for servicing new credit debt.

Here, we define and specify a housing loan. More precisely, the demand is defined as a specific purpose. The following purposes are considered as a housing loan: purchase of housing, business premise or building land, building/appendage/outbuilding of housing, renovating, refinancing of the housing loan by other bank. The news is that the purposes for purchasing a business premise or building land, and for renovating, are excluded from the purpose. At the same time, the purpose for refinancing a housing loan by the other bank remains, and “total maturity date” is introduced, which means a sum of the agreed date of the credit maturity and all extensions of the maturity date of that credit.

At the same time, with the hedged loans maximal repayment term is determined, for the housing loan it is 30 years, while for the consumer hedged credits there is a limit of 20 years. In parallel, it is determined that with the hedged loans, the maximal credit debt to be 85% with regard to the estimated value of the offered security, i.e. real estate.

An indicator TDTI has been introduced in the Decision (previously, some banks used DTI in the calculations as per their own methodology), as a ratio between the amount of the natural person’s total obligations based on the credit exposures of all banks and saving banks towards that person and the person’s total obligations towards other financial institutions on a monthly base.

Concerning the revenues, some corrections have been made from a time dimension point of view when the average monthly income is calculated. The banks used to calculate the average of the last three months, but with the changes now, they are obliged to calculate the average for income/pension inflows on the bank’s transaction account for at least last six months.

Concerning the incomes on other bases (as additional incomes, besides that from the regular employment or pension), for instance rents – leasing the property, temporary service contract – copyrights and similar rights, dividends, etc., it is defined that the incomes should be taken as an inflow of at least 6 months and they are taken up to maximum 80% on a net basis (gross income minus taxes, contributions and other expenses). Furthermore, it is foreseen for the bank to assess carefully the regularity and sustainability of those additional incomes.

Simulation of applying the new way of calculating when average for 3 months is changed to 6 months in case of salary change in the view of its increasing is presented in the following table²⁷:

Table 1. Simulation 1

before implementation		calculation according to Decision	
month	monthly income - salary	month	monthly income - salary
6	40.000	6	40.000
5	40.000	5	40.000
4	36.000	4	36.000
	116.000	3	36.000
	38.667	2	36.000
		1	36.000
			224.000
Difference	-1.333		37.333

month	monthly income - salary	month	monthly income - salary
6	40.000	6	40.000
5	36.000	5	36.000

²⁷ The calculations are made by the authors. In one of the cases, the calculation has been made for the three last months, 6,5,4 month of the year with an assumption of change, an increase of the monthly income from salary, for received one increased salary, while in the other case for received two increased salaries from 36,000 to 40,000 mkd, then calculations before implementing the Decision, and in the second part- calculations according to the Decision for the last 6 months.

4	36.000	4	36.000
	112.000	3	36.000
	<u>37.333</u>	2	36.000
		1	36.000
			<u>220.000</u>
Difference	-667		<u>36.667</u>

Source: authors' calculations

It is evident that in case of salary change in the view of its increasing, and in cases when the salary is increased and the credit applicant has received one or two increased salaries, there is a symbolic change in the capacity for servicing, i.e. if he (she) has received one (two) salary(ies), according to the new calculation the financially acceptable capacity for obligations servicing is decreased by 667 (1,333) mkd. Should we express this in relative indicators, the capacity for servicing decrease is 1,79% (3,45%).

Simulation of applying the new way of calculation when there is a change. The applicant has returned from sick leave after 5, 6 months (or there is a change in the salary).

Table 2. Simulation 2

before implementation		calculation according to Decision	
month	monthly income - salary	month	monthly income - salary
6	40.000	6	40.000
5	40.000	5	40.000
4	36.000	4	36.000
	116.000	3	36.000
	<u>38.667</u>	2	25.200
		1	25.200
			<u>202.400</u>
Difference	-4.933		<u>33.733</u>

month	monthly income - salary	month	monthly income - salary
6	40.000	6	40.000

5	36.000	5	36.000
4	36.000	4	36.000
	112.000	3	36.000
	37.333	2	25.200
		1	25.200
			198.400
Difference	-4.267		33.067

Source: authors' calculations

In such situations we have significant change in the capacity for servicing the obligations or we have decreased creditworthiness by 4,933 mkd or 4,267 mkd should one increased salary has been received. If we express this in relative indicators, the capacity for servicing decrease is 11,43% (12,76%).

Concerning the determination of the total monthly liabilities, according to the Decision, the banks are obliged:

- To consider the credit exposures where the monthly repayment is agreed;
- To determine repayment monthly amount for exposures where the frequency of monthly repayment is not predicted;
- To determine average monthly amount of repayment for exposures during the contract entire term including the highest interest rates, too;
- To determine monthly obligation on the basis of negative balances, according to the amount of the monthly obligation for an interest as per the actual interest rate;
- To determine monthly amount on the basis of credit cards and other revolving products, according to the monthly obligation amount of 3% of the total approved credit exposure.

An important change in the segment for determining total monthly obligations of natural persons compared to the previous individual calculation is determination of an average amount of monthly liabilities for credits that during their repayment term have fixed and variable interest rate. We shall make simulations and calculations for that.

Simulation of applying the new way of calculating the monthly obligations. Housing loan applicant for the amount of 3 million denars for 20 years and calculations before implementation of the new way of calculating and

calculations with fixed interest rates for 5/10 years and with variable interest rates.²⁸.

Table 3. Simulation 3

month	monthly installment	month	monthly installment
120	17.865	120	17.865
		120	20.682
240		240	
average monthly installment	<u>17.865</u>	average monthly installment	<u>19.273</u>
Difference	<u>1.408</u>		

month	monthly installment	month	monthly installment
120	17.865	60	17.865
		180	22.005
240		240	
average monthly installment	<u>17.865</u>	average monthly installment	<u>20.970</u>
Difference	<u>3.105</u>		

Source: authors' calculations

When determining the monthly obligations for potential credit exposure for a housing loan before implementing the measures, it is 17,865 mkd. The calculations, as per the new directions show higher level of monthly obligation. If the credit is with a fixed interest rate of 10 (5) years, it is 19,237 (20,970) mkd and higher level of monthly obligation by 1,408 (3,105) mkd. Should we express this in relative indicators, the increase of the monthly obligation compared to the initial one is 7,88% (17,40%).

²⁸ The calculations were made according to the average interest rates from the current housing loan offers from the websites of Stopanska banka AD Skopje, Komercijalna banka, NLB banka, Halk banka and Sparkasse Bank

We have determined the acceptable average monthly incomes (specifically only on the basis of a salary) and we have determined the monthly obligation (only on the basis of a housing loan) and with that we can proceed to implementation of the defined ratio according to the macro prudent instruments, the DSTI indicator that must not exceed 55% when approving a credit in denars and 50% when approving a credit in denars with a foreign exchange clause or a credit in foreign currency.

Of course, approvals of exception credit exposures are also foreseen, they are limited to maximum 10% of the total average quarterly amount of the bank's credit exposures determined for the last 12 months.

CONCLUSION

This is a systematized overview of implementing the macro prudent instruments when there is a change in the salary in the view of its increase or the person has used sick leave:

	reduction of financial potential	increasing the monthly obligation	
salary / pension	-3,45%	17,38%	home loan fixed with variable interest
sick leave	-11,43%		

The implementation of the Decision for macro prudent instruments for quality of the credit demand by the natural persons through concretely elaborated examples, points out to changes referring to financial potential decreasing, followed in parallel by the monthly obligation increase which limits the natural persons' maximal credit debt and makes preventive influence on potential over-indebtedness of the natural persons. The same, in the view of the credit risk relativization, maintaining a portfolio of high quality and healthy banking system.

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